

Part 5 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Modern restorations based on modern adhesives vs unbonded and strained dentine due to metallic screw, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon¹, David I Adam²

1 Ashty Teaching Hospital
Erbil, Kurdistan region, Iraq
mzsmaxillofacial@gmail.com
2 OSTEOOTECH UK LIMITED
London – UK
davidibrahamadam@gmail.com

Abstract

For decades, the screwable fiber post has been chosen as the gold standard after endodontic treatment. Screwable metallic posts lack 2 very important features: passivity after insertion, and no connection to the dentine. The use of the amalgam as the main restorative choice complicates the sequel, resulting in disastrous results that render the complications, namely, fracture of the tooth, unsalvageable. In this paper, we want to investigate these aspects from a mechanical perspective.

Keywords: Screwable post, Biomechanics, Amalgam, Endodontic, Root fracture, Strain, Strain energy density, Modulus of elasticity.

Introduction

Amalgam has been the gold standard restoration in the dental field for decades. (1). Amalgam had no bonding to the tooth structure, and in many cases could expose the teeth to stresses due to setting expansion. (2). According to the author's knowledge, no study simulating post-screwing or amalgam expansion had been presented in the scientific literature of biomechanics in endodontics.

The sequelae of both conditions are highly deleterious to the tooth structure. We want to pave the way to understand this issue, which has a crucial impact on clinical choices. In this paper, we want to investigate the effect of multiple factors on the performance of the endodontically treated teeth. One of the tested issues is the cusp capping, where it has been a proven maneuver to reduce or prevent highly anticipated tooth damage. (3). Other issues, such as post screwing and fiber reinforced vs metallic post, had been discussed in our previously published papers in this series. (4) (5)

Methods

We had tested 3 models

- Composite model
- Model of composite with cusp capping
- Amalgam models

Another variant was whether to use a screwable or cemented post.

Figure 1 The difference between the 3 models is apparent. The model on the left is the cusp capping model, the middle model is the composite model, and the model on the right is the amalgam model

We had not modeled amalgam as it had no bond to the dentine and enamel. With MOD restorations, we had these main defects in the tooth structures

- Loss of the connecting mesial and distal tooth structure that keeps the lingual portion attached to the buccal portion
- Weakening of the tooth structure
- The buccal cusp of the lower and the palatal cusp of the upper had been placed in a poor situation where no reinforcement was done to restrain them

Figure 2 This model represents the same as cusp capping.

In our previously published paper, we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the PD passively on the alveolar process.

Figure 3 As we have no bonding between the tooth structure and the amalgam, we made this model the amalgam model. The blue applicator over the cusp analogue is the adaptor where all forces are applied over it in all models.

Figure 4 The force was applied in an inclined direction.

Figure 5 In all of our models about biomechanics in endodontics, we had fixed the base.

The material properties had been the same in the previous models that had been presented in other papers in this series.

Results and discussions

We use the strain results to predict the failure mode of the domain.

Figure 6 This is the strain results. The first model on the left is just an expanded post without a load that simply represents the tightening of the screwable metallic post, 2nd model is the amalgam without the post, but the load is present. As the amalgam had no adhesion or bonding to the tooth structure, we had left the region empty. 3rd is the cusp capping model with soft post, 4th cusp capping with stiff post, 5th composite with soft post, 6th amalgam model with expanded post, and loads

The strain of the mastication model with amalgam restoration (model number 2) in the Figure 6 should be correlated with the frequently fractured lingula cusp of the lower molars and palatal cusp of the upper molar or even premolars (6) (7). We had discussed the strained root. In certain condition this would lead to a vertical root fracture, where the tooth could be converted into unsalvageable.

Figure 7 The strain energy density model gives insights into fatigue and the possible fracture, and the best solution to restore the teeth.

The strain energy density clearly shows that model 4 (casp capping model with stiff post) produces the least possible effect on the dentine. Dentine should always be presented as fatigue-limited material after endodontic treatment. (8). This had been found in an agreement with other studies. (9). Nevertheless, the last paper did not draw a clear conclusion that could be applied clinically.

The myopic biomechanical vision that makes the choice of more flexible posts against the same findings that represent the poor performance found in the same study clearly indicates either a conflict of interests or totally scientific disorientation. (10). This had been seen frequently in many studies, although they had depended upon criteria other than the currently used criteria. (11).

It is prudent to select the good criteria for a sound, robust result. Selection of different engineering criteria could lead to distraction and misleading as well as manipulation of the results, which is a highly biased maneuver. (12).

The advances in the development of dental adhesives have radically shifted the treatment toward new horizons. With these advancements, we should not be deceived by the marketing pressure and misleading results from contradictory researches.

Figure 8 Arrangement of the posts according to their modulus of elasticity, from highest with the ceramic on the left, then stainless steel, then titanium, and finally, on the right last plastic post

With different materials available in the market, we should always consider all the mechanical properties of the materials, especially Poisson's ratio and modulus of elasticity, as the stiffness had the upper arm of the determination of biocompatibility. (13)

Figure 9 Out of the box thinking. Modern manufacturing has enabled clinicians to handle even the most complicated cases effectively. Image provided courtesy of Dr. Ali Mueen and reproduced with permission.

Figure 10 Displacement indicates the stiffness.

In our current models, we don't want to emphasize the statistics, but rather to show the clear patterns that are presented with big differences. (14). We deeply think that the statistics are just an academic spice in the field of numerical simulations, as almost all studies are mesh-based (15).

We could conclude from the previous results that it seems that the worst possible scenario is when we are using an Amalgam filling with a screwable metallic post.

References

References

1. *Amalgam restoration of posterior teeth before endodontic treatment*. **Barkmeier W, Murrin J, Anderson R.** s.l. : Journal of Endodontics.
2. *SETTING EXPANSION OF AMALGAM: INFLUENCE OF THE DIRECTION OF CONDENSATION*. . **JORGENSEN KD, HOLST K.** s.l. : Acta Odontol Scand. , 1964.
3. *Longevity of Amalgam Build-Up Restorations in Endodontically Treated Teeth*. **Kermanshah, Hamid.** (. s.l. : Journal of Islamic Dental Association of IRAN. 132-138. 10.30699/IJsdreir.30.4.132. , 2018).
4. *Part 4 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), novel model simulating screwing of the metallic post inside the root of an endodontically treated tooth, Stupid models for interpreting living organs*. **Mohammed Zahid S., M.** (. s.l.: International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 2026).
5. *Part 3 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Effect of the endodontic post used on the dentine, soft vs stiffer material, novel approach via numerical model, Stupid models for interpreting living organs*. **Mohammed Zahid S., M.** (. s.l.: International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 2026).
6. *Influence of cusp coverage on the fracture resistance of premolars with endodontic access cavities*. **ElAyouti A, Serry MI, Geis-Gerstorfer J, Löst C.** S.l. : Int Endod J., 2011.
7. *Effect of Fiber Post and Cusp Coverage on Fracture Resistance of Endodontically Treated Maxillary Premolars Directly Restored with Composite Resin*. **Narmin Mohammadi, Mehdi Abed Kahnamoii, Parnian Karimi Yeganeh, Elmira Jafari Navimipour.** s.l. : Journal of Endodontics, 2009.
8. *Part 2 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Theoretical framework and development of computational model of dentine fatigue, Stupid models for interpreting living organs*. **Zahid S., M.** s.l. : International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), (2026).
9. *Finite element analysis of maxillary central incisors restored with various post-and-core applications*. **Seo M, Shon W, Lee W, Yoo HM, Cho BH, Baek SH.** s.l. : Restor Dent Endod. , 2009;34(4):324-332.
10. *Finite element analysis of a glass fibre reinforced composite endodontic post*. **A. Pegoretti, L. Fambri, G. Zappini, M. Bianchetti.** s.l. : Biomaterials, 2002.
11. *Influence of Ferrule, Post System, and Length on Biomechanical Behavior of Endodontically Treated Anterior Teeth*. **Santos-Filho P, Verissimo C, Soares P.** s.l. : Journal of Endodontics, 2013.
12. *The influence of elastic modulus mismatch between tooth and post and core restorations on root fracture*. **Ona, M &, Wakabayashi, Noriyuki & Yamazaki, T &, Takaichi, Atsushi, & Igarashi, Yoshimasa.** s.l. : International endodontic journal, (2012).
13. *Impact of Hip Arthroplasty Stiffness on the Biocompatibility*. **Saadoon, Mohammed Zahid.** s.l. : International Journal of Medical Science and Health Research, 2021.
14. *Clinicians' guide to statistics for medical practice and research: Part I*. **Krousel-Wood MA, Chambers RB, Muntner P.** s.l. : Ochsner J. , 2006.
15. *How different scenarios of a maxillary central incisor with endodontic microsurgery, fiber post, and periodontal loss affect biomechanical behavior: a finite element analysis study*. **Yanık, D., Türker, N. & Özarslan, M.** s.l. : BMC Oral Health 25, 802 (), 2025.
16. *Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Teeth as jaw weakeners: a pivotal concept in the biomechanics*. **Saadoon, M. Z.** (. s.l.: International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 1(2), 1–33., 2025).
17. *MOHAMMED BODIES` ANALYSIS FEA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS` DESIGN CRITERIA*. **Saadoon, M. Z.** (2020).

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024, he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronics. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth, and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties, as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as a maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, the largest secondary referral center in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.